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Analysis of Control Volume in a Bidimensional Flat Plate Aerodynamic
Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Determining the size of control volumes in a computational aerodynamic analysis is an extremely important factor. Using a large control volume, there are more elements in the mesh. In the other hand, if it is small, the boundary conditions along with the sizes of the elements can interfere in the results of the coefficients of lift C_L , drag coefficient C_D and aerodynamic moment coefficient C_M . In this way, the present work evaluated four sizes of control volume, maintaining the same size of the elements of the mesh used. The objective was to find a C-Grid control volume type that did not influence the results and that was not extremely large due to the computational demand, aiming also a quick response to solve the problem. In this context, the ANSYS Fluent software was used for the aerodynamic simulation of the inclined flat plate and obtaining the aerodynamic coefficients C_L , C_D and C_M . Therefore, the results were compared with experimental results in Goudeseune wind tunnel (SELIG; ROBERT; WILLIAMSON, 2011). Numerical results converged with the experimental data and thus a control volume size with low and acceptable error was determined.

INTRODUCTION

The control volume (CV) size has great effects in a CFD simulation because when it is too big, the computational cost could be high and sometimes exceed the available machine processing capacity, In the other hand, when the size of CV is too small it could affect the analysis and mask and/or lead to errors that even using mesh refining could not solve. For single-building models, the CV lateral and top boundaries must be distant 5 times of the building height (TOMINAGAA et al., 2008). Patel and Ramani (2015) concluded that a good domain size is at least 5 times the studied object in lateral and top direction and 15 times in the back direction. Hardie (2006) highlight the 10 times ratio in CFD aircraft analysis.

In this context, the present paper had the objective to analyze and size a C-GRID CV aiming a 2d isothermal aerodynamic analysis around a thin flat plate, ascertaining the aerodynamic coefficients: lift C_L , drag C_D and moment C_M to measure, compare and define the best CV size.

METHODOLOGY

The used methodology (Fig. 1) follows five steps: first: the CV was modelled and boundary conditions defined, second: the size variations of the CV were defined, third: the mesh sizes for a mesh study are defined, fourth: the simulations are taken and fifth: the analysis to check the results of simulations and eventually take more simulations.

Figure 1. Flow chart of work.

In this way, it was used a C-GRID domain (Fig. 2), widely used (BORDIN, 2014; TANG, 2008; TIAN, 2003). The model is a flat plate with chord of 300 mm and thickness 9.3 mm. The boundary conditions: prescribed velocity equivalent a 120,000 Reynolds number for inlet and zero pressure gauge for outlet; wall condition without slip at the flat plate (inclined 4 degrees to produce lift); zero gradient velocity up and down. The reference pressure was 1 atm (Fig. 2). This initial case used the $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model due to the flow transition, used by Bordin (2014) in a similar analysis.

Figure 2. C-Grid domain for aerodynamic analysis and boundary conditions for the thin flat plate of 300 mm chord.

The simulations were taken in four domains (Tab. 1) to verify the size influence in results.

Domain	D1	D2	D3	D4
R (mm)	1000	2000	4000	8000
Ratio 2R/chord	6	13	26	53

Table 1. Utilized domains.

The mesh pattern (Fig. 3) contain a fine mesh region around the flat plate. For the bigger domains, it was utilized the same size pattern of finite volumes.

Figure 3. Mesh refinement pattern.

In Tab. (2) the meshes were created to maintain the same element size, but keeping the main idea to have the same central refined area surrounding the flat plate Fig. (3).

Table 2. Meshes.

Mesh	Number of elements
1	32,248
2	74,272
3	169,708
4	384,000
5	864,000
6	1,944,000

The results were validated comparing the experimental flow data around a thin flat plate and Reynolds number 120.000 and the geometric ratio thickness per chord of 3.10% studied by Camille Goudeseune and Michael Goudeseune (SELIG; ROBERT; WILLIAMSON, 2011; WILLIAMSON et al., 2012).

Model and Governing equations

The fluid-dynamic domain is solved by the continuity, Navier-Stokes equations and related turbulence models when necessary. The considerations for the study case flow is 2d, steady, viscous, rotational and the air is modeled as a Newtonian fluid.

The continuity equation (Eq. 1) is obtained through the mass conservation principle applied in a fluid element (KUNDU, 2012). The first term in (Eq. 1) is the transient aspect of the local specific mass and the second is the specific mass flux divergent and is related to the liquid loss due to divergent flux in a point. So, in this analysis, the flow is taken steady.

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho u_i) = 0 \quad (1)$$

The Navier-Stokes momentum equation for a Newtonian fluid (Eq. 2) is demonstrated through the momentum conservation principle applied to a fluid element, obtaining the Cauchy equation and applying the constitutive equation for a Newtonian fluid (KUNDU, 2012). The first term on the (Eq. 2) equation is the fluid particle acceleration whose is equal to the sum of the interferences acting in the fluid particle: the second term is a fraction equal to the pressure loss (negative sign) along the flow field – in case of positive, the third term represents the sum of field forces action and the last, the viscous forces acting in a fluid particle.

$$\rho \frac{Du_j}{Dt} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_j} + \rho g_j + \mu \frac{\partial^2 u_j}{\partial x_j^2} \quad (2)$$

When turbulence occurs, the velocity and pressure equations (Eq. 3 and Eq. 4) are averaged from the *Reynolds decomposition*, in terms of a mean value (over bar term) and a fluctuation term (with primes) (SPEZIALE, 1991).

$$u_i = \bar{u}_i + u'_i \quad (3)$$

$$p_i = \bar{p}_i + p'_i \quad (4)$$

The continuity and RANS equations (Eq. 5 and Eq. 6) follow:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho \bar{u}_i) = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} + \nu \nabla^2 \bar{u}_i - \mu \frac{\partial^2 \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j} \quad (6)$$

Thus, the RANS equations closure problem arises: the Reynolds tensor term τ_{ij} . To solve the equations, the turbulence models propose assumptions and hypotheses to quantify such term in relation to the flow field mean velocity with additional equations.

The turbulent viscosity and diffusivity concepts were introduced by Boussinesq in 1877 and therefore developed by Prandtl and von Karman. When applied show satisfactory results for the most CFD cases.

The turbulence models can be classified as: turbulent viscosity model based (EVM), non-linear turbulent viscosity models (NLEVM) and differential stress models (DSM) those are based in the Reynolds stress transport models (RSTM) or in the second-order closure problem (SOC) (SODJA, 2007).

Other model classification is: algebraic, one equation or two equations, and some of these are based in the concepts explained before. The algebraic model is obtained through the mixture length idea. One example of one equation model was proposed by Kolmogorov and Prandtl and express the characteristic turbulent velocity constant and the kinetic energy loss rate (KUNDU, 2012). Some of the two equations models are: k- ϵ , k- ω , SST and modifications of themselves like: RNG k- ϵ , k- ω SST. One detailed approach of the models equations was omitted but can be found in the specific literature.

The resolution of equations is made in the numeric way by the finite volume method (FVM). The FVM is considered the evolution of the difference finite method (DFM) and is widely used in the CFD and easily applicable to non-structured mesh. The method discretizes the continuum domain in a finite number of small elements – mesh. Thus, apply the conservation equations in the integral form to each finite control volume centered in the nodal point, this strategy provides the integral conservation of the phenomena variables: mass, momentum and energy (ANSYS, 2013; PANTAKAR, 1980).

In order to evaluate the mesh quality, the *Grid Convergence Index* (GCI) was used – a method proposed by Roache (1994, 1997) based on the error calculus of a variable of interest for mesh with successive constant refinement. This index is derived from the Richardson generalized extrapolation and is widely used in CFD: Ali, Doolan and Wheatley (2009); Bordin (2014); Ramponi, Blocken and Angelotti (2013).

The refinement ratio for a non-uniform refined mesh is defined (Eq. 7). The convergence order p (Eq. 8) is calculated by the interest variable in each of meshes, the number 1 is the refined mesh and number 3 is the worst.

$$r_{eff} = \left(\frac{N_i}{N_{i+1}} \right)^{\frac{1}{Dim}} \quad (7)$$

$$p = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{f_3 - f_2}{f_2 - f_1}\right)}{\ln(r_{eff})} \quad (8)$$

The response at the boundary of the mesh convergence is given by the Richardson extrapolation (Eq. 9) and the mesh convergence index between two successive meshes 1 and 2 or 2 and 3 is (Eq. 10), where the safe factor FS is 1.25 when utilizes three meshes and 3.00 when two meshes are used (ROACHE, 1994, 1997). Finally, a good indicator for the solution convergence is when k (Eq. 11) approaches the unit.

$$f_0 \cong f_1 + \frac{f_1 - f_2}{r_{eff}^p - 1} \quad (9)$$

$$GCI_{i,i+1} = \frac{F_S}{r_{eff}^p - 1} \left| \frac{f_{i+1} - f_i}{f_i} \right| \quad (10)$$

$$k = \frac{GCI_{2,3}}{r_{eff}^p GCI_{1,2}} \quad (11)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation convergence is reached for the C_L in each one of the domains D1, D2, D3 and D4, and those respective meshes Fig (4). The difference between domains was significantly small but a quite difference for the refined mesh was realized. And, of course, when increasing the quality mesh the difference increases. It is important to note that the bigger domain D4 has a significantly loss in the last mesh refinement due to its own bigger size and low refinement when compared to the others.

Figure 4. Comparison of lift coefficients for four different domains size and experimental results by Goudeseune (SELIG; ROBERT; WILLIAMSON, 2011).

For a best comprehension about the domains, the relative error graph between each case and the experimental case can be analyzed Fig. (5). It shows that the D2 domain shows good results, about less than 5% for the most refined meshes and the bigger domains show similar errors.

Figure 5. Comparison of lift coefficients error, according to experimental data, for four different domains size. All domains follow the same behavior as the mesh is refined.

For the GCI analysis (Tab. 3), the meshes 4, 5 and 6 were selected, respectively 384k, 864k and 1,944k elements. The lift coefficient in the convergence limit is 0.498059 very close to the Goudeseune experimental data. The error is 0.188%.

Table 3. GCI analysis.

Richardson Extrapolation	0.498059
GCI₁₂	1.8265%
GCI₂₃	6.6931%
GCI_{23/r^p}GCI₁₂	1.0384

The pressure and velocity distributions (Figs. 6, 7 and 8) agree with the real physics. Can be noticed a stagnation point (red color in Fig. 6) in the leading edge of the flat plate where is the highest pressure point and zero velocity respectively. The low pressure area (green color in Fig. 6) stay above the flat plate, once it is inclined and producing lift force due to the overall pressure around the plate. In addition, the re-circulation region is present in the upper side plate located after the boundary layer separation, light blue color confined by the dark blue color region (Fig. 8).

Figure 6. Pressure distribution around the flat plate.

Figure 7. Velocity distribution around the flat plate.

Figure 8. Velocity distribution near the flat plate.

It is worth emphasizing the behavior of the C_D and C_M graphics (Figs. 9 and 10) in aerodynamic analysis. These coefficients presented the same C_L convergence behavior but due to the lack of experimental results it was not possible to make the same comparison as in the case of C_L .

Figure 9. Comparison of drag coefficients for four different domains size.

Specifically, the moment aerodynamic coefficient data of the experimental results (WILLIANSON et al., 2012) has a little gap in the 4° angle of attack and the results jumps from -0.01 to -0.03 in the surroundings of this angle (Fig. 11). So, this is the reason to the jump behavior in results (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. Comparison of aerodynamic moment coefficients for four different domains size.

Figure 11. Experimental data of lift and moment aerodynamic coefficient (WILLIANSON et al., 2012).

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

Through this domain analysis and mesh refinement it was possible to define the best domain D2 (13 times ratio) for the aerodynamic analysis in study with acceptable low error according to experimental data and also relative to the GCI method. This result is very important

to prevent interference in the CFD results. These ratios of fluid domain could be utilized for the specific angle of attack studied or less, once the turbulence intensity and the flow separation on the flat plate is small. The same occur for the variable Reynolds number. Of course, is important to remember the thickness ratio 3.1%.

Once, the scape area in CV is square (Fig. 2), it is important to account that we could modify the top boundary to reduce the height. The pressure and velocity gradient area (Figs. 6, 7 and 8) is smaller than 2 times ratio, it is suggested to use 3 times ratio.

For future work, it is proposed and is already in study the verification of enlarge the angle of attack range, flow intensity, refine the control volume ratio size and confirm the 3 times height size.

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